

HOW HEAT TREATMENT AFFECTS THE CHROMATIC RESPONSE OF CARBON NANOTUBE – POLYDIACETYLENE COMPOSITES TO ELECTRICAL STIMULUS

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ABSTRACT

The science of multi walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) – polydiacetylene (PDA) composites that can change colour from blue to red under electrical stimulus is relatively new and not deeply explored. We studied the effects of heat treatment on the electrically induced transition in MWCNT-PDA composites. X-ray diffraction revealed that heating at 40°C prior to photo polymerization of diacetylene caused the peak intensities to become remarkably intense, suggesting improved order in the polymer film. From in-situ absorption spectra, it was observed that the critical transition voltage increased significantly for pre-heated samples. Moreover, the absence of drift in the in-situ absorbance spectra of annealed samples suggests that heat treatment reduces the ability of PDA to respond collectively to electrical stimulus. In-situ Raman spectra at the critical transition voltage revealed that pre-heat treatment improves the ability of PDA to restore alignment upon removal of electrical stimulus. Pre-heat treatment is thus thought to improve the electrochromic response of MWCNT-PDA composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Diacetylene monomers under favorable orientation undergo rapid solid state polymerization upon UV irradiation to yield blue polydiacetylene (PDA). This blue phase, when subjected to stimuli such as heat, mechanical force and foreign molecules, switch to a red phase [1-15]. Typically, the blue to red transition in PDA is irreversible. Interestingly, PDA when combined with dry spun multi walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) bundles undergo blue to red electrochromism reversibly for up to 14 current cycles [16]. However, practical applications of these composites require a higher degree of control over the reversibility and critical transition voltage in these composites. Heat treatment, specifically heat treatment before polymerization has been shown to be effective to improve the ordered layer structure of PDA films [17, 18]. In this work, we investigated the effects of heat treatment on the electrochromic response of MWCNT-PDA composites. In-situ absorption and Raman spectroscopy were used to evaluate the subtle differences in the electrically induced transition of composites with and without heat treatment. Based on morphological differences, in-situ spectroscopy and Raman mapping before and after current flow, it seems like pre-heat treatment improves the chromatic response of MWCNT-PDA composites towards electrical stimulus.

2 MATERIALS

MWCNT forests were grown on a Fe-Al₂O₃ catalyst using a chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method as described elsewhere [19-22]. The process involved sputter deposition of a 30 nm buffer Al₂O₃ layer followed by 1 nm of Fe onto polished silicon wafer. As prepared catalyst was inserted into the quartz tube of a CVD furnace and annealed at 750°C to initiate breaking up of the Fe layer into uniform nanoparticles. Subsequently, ethylene was passed through the tube, to initiate the growth of vertically aligned MWCNT arrays. Horizontally aligned MWCNT sheets were drawn from these forests and transferred onto glass substrates as illustrated in Figure 1. DA monomer 10,12-PCDA, purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Singapore, was dissolved in Tetrahydrofuran (THF) at a concentration of 10 mg/mL and cast onto the aligned MWCNT sheets, dried overnight in air and subjected to UV-254 nm irradiation to yield composite I. For composite II, UV irradiation was followed by heat treatment at 40°C, for 1 h. The heat treatment was carried out prior to UV-254 nm irradiation to form composite III. Conductive silver paint (RS Components-1863600) was used to provide metallic contacts on the ends of the samples to facilitate current flow for in-situ spectroscopic measurements.

Figure 1: Scheme illustrating the fabrication steps for MWCNT-PDA composites used in this study.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphology

The morphology of MWCNT-PDA composites varied significantly as a consequence of heat treatment when compared to pure MWCNT sheets (Figure 2a). Composites prepared through route I appeared to have a uniform coating of polymer on MWCNT bundles (Figure 2b). Heating at 40°C for an hour of such composites resulted in a structure wherein the polymer spread across neighboring bundles (Figure 2c). It is important to note that this apparent spreading is not due to PDA melting, as PDA retains its physical state at much higher temperatures. A similar heat treatment prior to UV polymerization resulted in large sections of the composite with morphologies as shown in Figure 2d; the monomers in this case appear to have infiltrated the gaps within MWCNT bundles much more effectively.

As heat treatment has been used to improve polymer film characteristics [17, 18], we expected the crystal structure to be altered in response to heat treatment. The X-ray diffractograms of composites I, II and III were indeed different (Figure 3). Diffraction patterns were apparent for I, II and III, suggesting that PDA films generally have periodic ordered layer structures, in agreement with literature [17, 18, 23]. However, the intensities of the pre-heated composite (III) were much stronger, implying the ordered layer structure was enhanced.

Figure 2: Field emission scanning electron micrographs of (a) pure MWCNT sheet, (b) PDA-MWCNT prepared through route I, (c) route II and (d) route III. The scale bar corresponds to 50 μm .

Figure 3: XRD patterns of composite I, II and III.

3.2 In-situ Absorption Spectroscopy

In-situ spectroscopy has been shown to be useful to understand the kinetics of chromatic transitions in solvatochromic and thermochromic PDA [24, 25]. In this study, MWCNT-PDA composites exposed to different heat treatments were subjected to progressively increasing voltages and their changes in absorbance recorded. Before applying voltage, all the composites, irrespective of the route of synthesis, exhibited an absorbance peak at 650 nm, which is characteristic of the blue phase of PDA. Current flow caused a decrease in intensity of the blue peak and a simultaneous increase in intensity of the peak at 540 nm, characteristic of the red phase of PDA, for all cases. However, two features of the absorbance transition stood out: (i) for composite I, current flow caused significant downward shifts of the entire absorbance spectra when compared to composites prepared through routes II and III (Figure 4a-c) and (ii) the critical transition voltage increased from 10 V to 16 V for composite III, when compared to I and II (Figure 4d-f). Downward drift of the absorption spectra over the entire wavelength range is indicative of collective behavior of the PDA layer. This is not surprising as PDA assemblies are known to exhibit collective responses to stimuli. What is interesting is that the collective phenomenon appears to decrease substantially in the annealed composites II and III. A possible explanation is that the PDA film breaks up into smaller, independent segments in the case of composites II and III.

Figure 4: In-situ absorbance change with voltage for PDA-MWCNT composites prepared via (a) route I, (b) route II and (c) route III and the corresponding critical transition voltages (d-f).

3.3 Raman Spectroscopy

3.3.1 In-situ Raman

The conjugated nature of the back-bone of PDA makes it ideal for characterization using Raman spectroscopy as double and triple bonds of carbon give distinct Raman shifts at around 1450 and 2080 cm^{-1} , respectively [26]. Typically, red phase of PDA exhibits red-shifted peaks for both $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ [27]. Hence, tracking the intensity and shift of the prominent carbon peaks could reveal a lot about the physical aspects of the chromatic transition in MWCNT-PDA composites.

It should be noted that in this in-situ Raman investigation, point spectra centered at 1450 cm^{-1} was obtained, as $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ is the most prominent peak in the PDA Raman spectrum. We learnt from the in-situ absorption studies that the critical transition voltage for composites I and II was 10 V while that for III was 16 V. The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ of these composites before, during and after removing 10 V (for I and II) and 16 V (for III) were thus compared. The Typical peak profiles before, during and after applying the critical transition voltage for composite I, II and III are shown in figure 5. The most striking observation was that before applying voltage bias, the intensity was highest for composite II. This corresponds to the morphology shown in figure 2c, where the PDA segments appear to spread across neighboring bundles. A closer look at the peaks under voltage bias reveals that for composites I and III, there was hardly any difference while for II, the intensity decreased substantially. Removal of voltage bias caused a recovery of peak intensities for I and III, while for II, caused a drastic decrease. The peak intensity is indicative of the alignment of PDA on MWCNT, with high intensities suggesting more PDA is aligned along the laser polarization (MWCNT) direction. Hence, from the peak profiles in figure 5, it can be interpreted that post heat treatment improves the degree of motion of PDA chains under electrical stimulus, but hinders recovery of initial PDA alignment upon removal of stimulus. Pre-heat treatment however does not improve the degree of motion of PDA chains, but improves the ability of PDA to recover alignment along MWCNT upon stimulus removal.

Figure 5: Evolution of $\nu_{C=C}$ of MWCNT-PDA composites prepared via (a) route I, (b) route II and (c) route III, before, during and after the critical transition voltage.

3.3.2 Raman mapping

The strong Raman shifts originating from the conjugated backbone of PDA permits mapping of a specified area of the composite sample to gauge the polymer distribution prior to and after current flow. As the incident laser beam (633 nm) is polarized along the horizontal axis (along the MWCNT alignment direction for our composites), intense Raman peaks imply the PDA is aligned along the laser polarization direction, i.e. along the MWCNTs. We tracked the intensity of the most prominent PDA peak, $\nu_{C=C}$ at 1450 cm^{-1} , over an area of $50\text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$.

The Raman maps obtained before and after current flow for composites I, II and III are shown in figure 6. All maps had distinct bright regions, which denote the polymer segments aligned along the laser polarization direction, as explained earlier. Even to the untrained eye, there appeared to be subtle differences in the bright regions after the critical transition potential was applied for 5 seconds. By quantifying the bright sections of these maps using ImageJ software, we found that prior to current flow, composites I, II and III had 72.67, 73.67 and 77.67 % of PDA aligned the underlying MWCNTs. After current flow, the percent PDA alignment changed to 73.92, 82.48 and 75.43 %, respectively (Figure 7). Hence, for composites I and II, current flow resulted in more PDA being aligned along underlying MWCNTs while for III, there was a decrease in PDA alignment by 2.3 %.

The absorption spectra of composite I underwent drastic downward drift over the entire wavelength range and removal of the critical transition voltage further enhanced the downward drift (Figure 4a). This suggests that the PDA layer of I shows a collective behavior, with the absorption of the entire film reducing irreversibly under current flow. While the downward drift occurs for composites II and III, the magnitude of the drift is considerably reduced (Figure 3b and c). In fact, the drift is almost negligible in the blue end of the spectra for composite III. It thus seems likely that heat treatment (both before and after UV irradiation) reduces the ability of the PDA layer to respond collectively. This

could be a consequence of the altered PDA and MWCNT interaction in composites II and III as evidenced by the FESEM images (Figure 2c and d).

Figure 6: Optical image (left), Raman map before (middle) and after (right) current flow for composites (a) I, (b) II and (c) III. The scale bar corresponds to 20 μm .

Figure 7: Calculated percentage alignment of PDA along underlying MWCNTs before and after current flow in composites I, II and III.

Although heat treatment reduces the collective response of MWCNT-PDA composites, the significant increase in critical transition voltage of composite III points towards a different transition dynamic in this case. De-stacking of π -orbitals at the MWCNT-PDA interface is the likely origin of electrochromism in these composites. If the transition proceeds at a lower voltage, it means that de-stacking of π -orbitals occurs fairly easily. In our case, composites I and II undergo the transition at 10 V while III, at 16 V (Figure 4d-f). Hence, de-stacking of π -orbitals requires a higher current flow for composite III. This is unexpected as pre-heat treatment seems to improve the interaction between PDA and MWCNT (Figure 2d), implying a more efficient interaction of π -electrons at the interface, and consequently, de-stacking at lower potential bias. A likely explanation is that the PDA segments in composite III are much smaller than the other two cases. Electrochromic transition in such a system

will require de-stacking of π -orbitals of a large number of small PDA segments as opposed to few large segments in composites I and II, accounting for the increased critical transition voltage.

Figure 8: Proposed structures of MWCNT-PDA composites with no heat treatment (I), post-heat treatment (II) and pre-heat treatment (III). UV irradiation produces a surface coating of PDA on underlying MWCNTs (I). Post-heat treatment breaks up large PDA segments and spreads them across neighboring MWCNT bundles (II). Pre-heat treatment facilitates intercalation of monomers into the gaps between MWCNT bundles, resulting in high π -stacking interactions at the MWCNT-PDA interface after UV irradiation (III).

Based on the morphological analysis and spectroscopic results, we propose the following structural differences in MWCNT-PDA composites I, II and III. For composite I, UV irradiation results in long PDA segments aligned more or less along the axis of underlying MWCNT. Heat treatment after polymerization breaks up the large segments and spreads them across neighboring MWCNT bundles in the case of composite II. When heat treatment precedes the UV polymerization process (Composite III) the DA monomers aggregate as small clusters which align along MWCNTs as well as intercalate the gaps between bundles, with a high degree of stacking. The effectiveness of non-covalent interaction between the polymer and MWCNT, or in other words, π -stacking efficiency, is likely to be significantly influenced by these structural changes induced by heat treatment treatments. We expect the π -stacking to be minimum in composite I, where the DA monomers simply aggregate along the MWCNT sheet prior to UV irradiation. Heat treatment after polymerization as in the case of composite II, spreads the broken up polymerized segments across neighboring MWCNT bundles, with an accompanied slight increase in π -stacking at the interface. When heat treatment precedes UV polymerization (composite III), the DA monomers intercalate between neighboring MWCNT bundles, resulting in a structure with much higher π -stacking efficiency than I and II, after UV polymerization. However, the considerably reduced collective behavior of the PDA layer in III suggests that the PDA segments are much shorter than I and II. A higher critical transition voltage is required in this case to cause de-stacking in many small PDA segments as opposed to few large PDA segments in I and II, to realize the electrochromic transition.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effects of heat treatment on the electrochromic response of MWCNT-PDA composites were investigated. Morphology comparisons revealed the possible breaking up and spreading of large PDA segments onto neighboring MWCNT bundles after heat treatment. In-situ absorption studies revealed a direct link between critical transition voltage and heat treatment, with pre-heated MWCNT-PDA composites exhibiting a higher critical transition voltage of 16 V as opposed to 10 V for both un-annealed and post-annealed composites. Evolution of Raman shift ν_{C-C} before, during and upon removal of the critical transition voltage suggested that post heat treatment improved the degree of motion of PDA chains while pre-heat treatment improved the ability of PDA chains to recover initial alignment when voltage was removed. We propose that pre-heat treatment improves the electrochromic response of MWCNT-PDA composites owing to a structure with high degree of π -stacking, brought about by monomers intercalating the gaps between MWCNT bundles prior to photo polymerization.

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